

**PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE ORGANIZATION OF
PROPER MOVEMENT IN EMERGENCY SITUATIONS**

Mamadboev Shokrukh Bakhodirjonovich

Namangan state university

E-mail: mamadboyev@mail.ru

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Analyzes show that the number of emergency situations in our country is increasing year by year. For example, in 2020-2021, large-scale disasters in our country include the destruction of the Sardoba reservoir, strong winds in the Bukhara region, the worsening of the epidemiological situation in our country, and carbon monoxide poisoning. In the mentioned cases, we can even see that among the victims, among those who died, there were young students. Taking into account the above, it can be noted that reducing such situations among students and young people, developing students' skills of correct movement in emergency situations, researching improving the technology of controlling students' correct movement in emergency situations is becoming one of the urgent issues. So, on the basis of the given information, students are instructed to move and manage properly in emergency situations.

The Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Protection of the Population and Territories from Natural and Man-made Emergency Situations" and "On Civil Protection" define the preparation of the population to act in emergency situations as the most important task. Also the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Decree No. 5066 of June 1, 2017 "On measures to fundamentally improve the efficiency of the system of prevention and elimination of emergency situations" addressed a number of problems in the prevention of emergency situations. In particular, "... the fact that the scientific and research potential of the republic is not being used in practice in solving problems related to the protection of the population and territories from natural disasters and man-made accidents" and "... the training, retraining and the problem that their system of professional development does not meet modern requirements" is mentioned.

Decree No. 60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 2, 2017 "On further improvement of the system of training specialists in the field of protection of the population and territories from emergency situations" Decision

No. 3030, Decision No. 754 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 9, 2019, Decision No. 515 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 26, 2020, and other normative legal documents related to this field, this research work serves to a certain extent.

A lot of empirical and extreme data on determining the situational understanding of individual behavior has been collected within various scientific directions. The most common definition of a situation in foreign psychology is a space-time construct, a situation is a set of environmental elements or a fragment of the environment at a certain stage of a person's life.

D. Magnusson proposes to distinguish five levels of situations:

1. Stimuli, that is, certain objects and actions of the external environment.
2. Episodes, i.e. special events with cause and effect.
3. Physical, temporal and psychological parameters of the situation determined by external conditions. Perception and interpretation of the situation gives importance to stimuli and episodes.
4. Environment (setting) is a generalizing concept that describes types of situations.
5. Environment - a set of physical and social variables of the external world.

There is another position, so J. J. Mead, P. Berger and T. Lukman's works show that a person is an active "component" of any life situation. Even determining the essence of the situation for a person appears in the process of self-awareness or in the process of communicating with other people.

Situations are not passive here - they are actively perceived and discussed, they are dynamic; one person defines the situation for another and vice versa. From this point of view, the situation is a system of objective and subjective elements combined at a certain time in the life of the subject.

The Russian scientist Osukhova explained the concept of the situation as follows in her research. The concept of situation (Latin situs - position, situation) has entered the sciences to explain the situations of a person and his behavior, but despite the wide application of the concept of situation, the concept of "situation" is not always unambiguously and clearly interpreted. The concept of "situation" is often used as a synonym for the concept of "environment". Let's describe each of them in order to avoid ambiguity of these concepts. Environment is a set of certain conditions outside of a person, and a situation always includes a person. Situation types do not correspond to environment

types. The environment is characterized by stability and duration of influence, while the situation is a short-term sphere of influence. The environment is not always subjective, but the situation is subjective always "someone's situation". All this shows that these concepts are not the same and cannot be used as synonyms

K. Levin believes that the concept of the situation should be subjective rather than objective. Because the situation should be described not from the position of the observer, but from the position of the person whose behavior is being studied. The research of K. Levin and his students laid the foundation for the tradition of experimental study of human behavior in various life situations.

When studying the concepts related to the emergency situation, some authors use them as synonyms. A.F. Maydykov uses the term "extreme situation" instead of the term "emergency situation".

E.M. Babosov also describes it as extreme. In his opinion, such a situation is "a sudden, abrupt transition of the system (technological, social, economic, ecological, personal, etc.) as a result of an excessive increase in internal or external tension from a stable state to an unstable state, which threatens the collapse of this system".

T.S. Nazarova and B.S. Shapovalenko proposed to interpret the term "extreme situation" as "an extraordinary critical situation that requires an insignificant (unusual, unique) solution to get out of it". From the above interpretation, we can see that the concept of "emergency" can be considered close in meaning, because it is usually understood as an unexpected situation that requires immediate action.

Such an idea about the definition of an emergency situation, it is true, reflects some of its important features - it is suddenness, unpredictability, the need to take measures, etc., but it is still widespread.

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